

STUDIES ON THE SEED CAKE OF *ANNONA SQUAMOSA* (SITAPHAL)
PART I. THE NITROGENOUS CONSTITUENTS
OF THE SEED CAKE

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The defatted seed cake of *Annona squamosa* which contains 4.6% nitrogen and 21% protein, has been analysed for its nitrogenous constituents. A papain hydrolysate of the cake, water-extracts of the cake and acid hydrolysates of the seed proteins have been analysed for various nitrogen fractions.

The custard apple, *Annona squamosa* (Linn.) (Sitaphal), grows extensively in Hyderabad State. The fruit, which is considered very tasteful, has a large number of discrete, curved, fleshy fingers, each containing a single seed enclosed in a thin membranous covering. The seeds, which are shiny, greyish brown, flattish and elliptic, are about 2 cm. long and weigh about 0.3 g. each. The kernel which constitutes about 68.5% of the seed weight has been shown¹ to contain 40% of an oil and 19% of protein. The whole seed is inedible owing to an insecticidal principle associated with the oil². However, a non-toxic cake, rich in nitrogen, is obtained by extracting the fat-soluble insecticidal principle along with the oil by light petroleum. The utilisation of this cake is being studied in the Central Laboratories, and as a part of this study, an analysis of the solvent-extracted cake with reference to its nitrogenous constituents has been undertaken.

This communication deals with the work carried out on the defatted cake on the following lines: (i) Analysis of the non-protein nitrogenous fractions of the water extract of the cake, (ii) isolation of the protein and analysis of the protein hydrolysate, and (iii) hydrolysis of the cake by papain and determination of the nitrogenous fractions of the hydrolysate. Further work on the amino-acid composition of the protein and the biological evaluation of the proteins by feeding experiments will be reported in later papers.

EXPERIMENTAL

Shelled seeds of *A. squamosa*, pressed mechanically to remove oil and stored in the form of cakes, were used in these experiments. The cakes were ground to a powder (60 mesh) and extracted with cold light petroleum (b.p. 40°-80°). The defatted meal was then air-dried and stored in air-tight containers.

The proximate composition of the cake, analysed by the usual methods, is shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Proximate composition of the defatted seed meal.

Moisture	7.76%	Ash	5.41%
Nitrogen*	4.86	Fibre and	
Protein (N × 6.25)	30.38	carbohydrates	56.4

*Micro-kjeldahl method using the digestion mixture of Cbibnal, Rees and Williams³.

Non-protein nitrogenous constituents of the cake.—The fractionation of these constituents was effected by a method originally described by Wasteneys and Borsook⁴, with some modifications. The terms proteose, peptone and peptide employed in Table II give an idea of the percentage of protein nitrogen present at the various levels of breakdown, and the precipitability and molecular complexity of the fractions.

The defatted meal was extracted by shaking in a mechanical shaker for two hours, at room temperature, with six times its weight of distilled water. The mixture was then centrifuged and the centrifugate separated. The residue was again extracted with water, as before, and the extractions were repeated five times in all. The combined centrifugates from the extractions were filtered through paper pulp to furnish a clear solution.

The total nitrogen in the water extract was calculated by determination of the N in aliquot parts of the filtrate. Heat-coagulable proteins were precipitated by heating the extract for 30 minutes in a steam steriliser, after adjusting the p_H to 4.6 with hydrochloric acid (1 N). The precipitate was filtered off after cooling the extract and the heat-stable N in the filtrate was determined. The filtrate (800 c.c.) was then concentrated under reduced pressure and the volume made up to 100 c.c.

To 40 c.c. aliquots of the concentrate was added 10 c.c. of a freshly prepared solution of trichloroacetic acid (12.5%), and the mixtures allowed to stand for one hour. The contents were filtered and the filtrate heated in boiling water to decompose the trichloroacetic acid and to drive off the chloroform and carbon dioxide resulting from it. The filtrate was then cooled and made up to 50 c.c. and nitrogen determined in aliquot lots. This represented the non-protein nitrogen in the extract.

The trichloroacetic acid filtrate (30 c.c.) was then treated with sodium sulphate (20 g.) and allowed to stand at 34° for one hour. After filtering the contents at the end of this period, the nitrogen in the filtrate (which was made up to 50 c.c.) was determined in aliquots. The 'proteose' nitrogen is the difference between the nitrogen in the trichloroacetic acid filtrate and the sodium sulphate filtrate.

The sodium sulphate filtrate was then treated with sodium hydroxide, followed by tannic acid dissolved in 0.1 N sulphuric acid containing 20% sodium sulphate and kept for four hours; at the end of this period, it was rapidly filtered and the N in the filtrate determined. A blank with the same reagents was also run and N estimated. After allowing for the blank, the difference in the N contents of the sodium sulphate filtrate and the tannic acid filtrate represented 'peptone' nitrogen.

To the tannic acid filtrate (50 ml.), made 5% acidic with sulphuric acid, phosphotungstic acid (4.5 g.) was added. The precipitate was centrifuged after keeping overnight, and washed with a solution of phosphotungstic acid (2.5% in 5% sulphuric acid). The centrifugate was shaken with baryta to remove the phosphotungstic acid and with sulphuric acid to precipitate barium. The brown solution obtained finally was made up to a known volume and nitrogen estimated in aliquots. The results are summarised in Table II.

TABLE II

Fractionation of the water extract into the various constituents.

	Amount.	N as % of N in water extract.	N as % of non-protein N.
1. Total nitrogen in the water extract	387.0 mg.	...	...
2. Heat-coagulated N	221.6	57.25	...
3. Heat stable N	165.4	42.75	...
4. Non-protein N	163.9	42.35	...
5. 'Proteose' N	21.0	5.42	12.81
6. Peptone N	21.9	5.65	13.36
7. Simple peptides and bases N	6.1	1.58	3.72
8. Residual N	114.9	29.70	70.11

The non-protein N in the water extract was found to be 163.9 mg., out of the total N in the water extract of 387.0 mg. Out of the balance of 223.1 mg. N taken as due to protein, it is seen that 221.6 mg. are heat-coagulated. Making allowance for the non-protein N in the water extract, it may be computed that if the rest of the N in the cake be taken to be protein N, the cake contains 20.9% of protein, of which 63.5% is water extractable.

Extraction of Protein from the Seed cake and Hydrolysis of the Protein

The protein of *A. squamosa* seed cake was extracted in separate experiments with aqueous solutions of sodium sulphite and sodium hydroxide. It was found that the protein extracted by NaOH gradually darkened in colour on keeping, whereas that obtained by extraction with sodium sulphite remained light in colour. For further analysis of the protein by hydrolysis, it was therefore decided to use the protein obtained from the cake by sodium sulphite extraction.

Extractions of protein from vegetable seeds by aqueous solutions of sodium sulphite have been reported earlier by Kodangekar, Mandlikar and Mehta⁴ and by others. It was found that a 0.3% aqueous sodium sulphite solution, used in two lots, proved optimum for this purpose.

The extraction of the protein was carried out in the following way. The powdered defatted seed cake was preliminarily leached with a 0.1% acetic acid solution to remove soluble salts of calcium, magnesium etc. (according to the procedure of Satow⁶). The leached meal was thoroughly stirred with ten times its weight of 0.3% sodium sulphite solution for two hours, its p_H having been maintained at 7.0. At the end of this period, the mixture was allowed to settle and most of the supernatant liquid decanted off. The residue was treated a second time with sodium sulphite solution and the combined extracts were filtered and sulphur dioxide passed through till the p_H fell to 4.5. The precipitated protein was allowed to settle and, after filtration, washed with alcohol and ether and dried at 50°.

Hydrolysis of the Protein

The procedure of Van Slyke⁷ was closely followed with a few necessary modifications. The protein was hydrolysed by refluxing for 18 hours with 20% hydrochloric acid. The hydrolysate, thus obtained, was concentrated under reduced pressure to a syrupy solution and made up to a known volume with water. The nitrogen in the hydrolysate was determined in small aliquots. Then to a known quantity of the hydrolysate in a double necked distillation flask were added alcohol and a 10% suspension of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, till it was alkaline. The mixture was distilled at 30 mm. pressure, and the evolved ammonia absorbed in a known volume of $N/10\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$. The amide nitrogen in the hydrolysate was calculated from the amount of ammonia liberated in this operation.

The residue in the Claisen flask was filtered, washed and along with the filter paper submitted to analysis by the Kjeldahl method. This value represents melanin nitrogen.

The filtrate from melanin was neutralised with HCl and concentrated under reduced pressure. It was taken up in a flask and mixed with HCl (conc.) and phosphotungstic acid (PTA) and made up with water so that the PTA concentration was 7.5%. The mixture was heated till the precipitates were nearly in solution and then allowed to stand for 48 hours. The resultant precipitate was filtered under suction to dryness, washed with a solution containing 2.5% PTA and 3.5% HCl . The precipitate was then transferred to a separating funnel and after addition of HCl (conc.), extracted with a mixture of amyl alcohol and ether⁸ (1:1) three times. The aqueous layers were collected, concentrated under reduced pressure and made up to a known volume.

Arginine nitrogen was estimated in an aliquot of the solution by refluxing it with KOH for six hours and absorbing the evolved ammonia in a known volume of standard sulphuric acid. The alkali solution was distilled in the Kjeldahl distillation apparatus to collect and absorb any residual ammonia.

The solution left after distillation for arginine nitrogen was submitted to a Kjeldahl digestion and nitrogen determined. Total basic nitrogen was calculated from this value plus the arginine value.

Cystine nitrogen was determined in an aliquot by evaporating it in a dish with Denis' solution⁹ to dryness and on further heating to redness sulphur was estimated as barium sulphate. Nitrogen in the PTA filtrate was determined in aliquots. The results of this analysis are presented in Table III. The complete composition of the amino-acid digest will be reported later.

TABLE III

Hydrolysis of A. squamosa protein by conc. HCl.

Protein taken = 2.371 g.

	Amount. (mg.)	As% of total N in hydrolysate.
N in the acid hydrolysate	366	...
Amide-N	25.0	6.83
Melanin-N	3.4	0.91
Arginine-N	68.8	18.8
Cystine-N	5.1	1.39
Histidine- and lysine-N	36.8	10.0
N in phosphotungstic acid filtrate	227.0	62.02

Hydrolysis of the Cake by Papain and Analysis of the Hydrolysate

Papain-hydrolysed proteins and proteinaceous materials have found a variety of uses, in diets, medicine, bacteriological media etc. In a study of the fermentation of molasses to lactic acid on a pilot plant scale, carried out in our laboratories, it became necessary to explore the possibilities of employing cheap accessory nutrients for this fermentation. Since laboratory tests had shown that papain-hydrolysates of soyabean were very satisfactory for this purpose, it was thought worthwhile to prepare a papain digest of the sitaphal cake and study its usefulness in this fermentation. Such a hydrolysate was prepared and found to be a satisfactory supplement to the molasses medium employed in this fermentation. The nitrogen distribution in one such hydrolysate was examined by the usual methods and described below.

The powdered seed cake (20 g.) was thoroughly mixed in a round-bottomed flask with water (150 c.c.) and papain (0.5 g.). After attaching a reflux condenser, the contents were vigorously shaken for about 15 minutes and then heated in a water-bath, maintained at 70°-75° for 5 hours with frequent shaking. H₂SO₄ (15 c.c. of 0.5 N) was then added and the well-mixed

contents were boiled for 15 minutes under reflux and then filtered hot. The residue was washed with small portions of hot water, and the combined filtrate, which was slightly turbid, repassed through a filter. The clarified solution, thus obtained, was made up to 250 c.c. with water containing a little chloroform. The hydrolysate gave a positive test with the biuret reagent.

The hydrolysate was then analysed as follows. The total solids were determined by drying 10 c.c. aliquots at 100° to constant weight. Total nitrogen was estimated by the micro-kjeldahl method. Amide nitrogen was determined in aliquots of the hydrolysate according to the procedure of Damodaran¹⁰. The Sørensen formol-titration method¹¹ was used for determination of amino nitrogen. The composition of the papain digest is recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV

	(g./250 c.c. of hydrolysate.)	As % of total N.
Total solids	6.31	—
Total nitrogen	0.507	—
Amide-nitrogen	0.012	2.4
Amino-nitrogen	0.148	29.2
PTA precipitable nitrogen	0.402	79.3
Nitrogen in PTA filtrate	0.105	20.7

C O N C L U S I O N S

The defatted seed cake of *A. squamosa* contains 4.86% nitrogen. In this respect it is not so rich as groundnut cake or soyabean cake. The cake contains 20.9% of protein, 2/3 of which (63.5%) is extracted by water, the remainder being extractable by dilute salt solutions. About a third of the amino-acid nitrogen is present in the form of basic amino-acid nitrogen. The papain-hydrolysate of the cake has been successfully employed as an accessory nutrient in the lactic fermentation of sugarcane molasses.

R E F E R E N C E S

1. Naidu & Achaya, *this Journal*, 1951, 14, 53.
2. Naidu *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1953, 16, 179.
3. Chibnal, Rees & Williams, *Biochem. J.*, 1943, 37, 354.
4. Wasteneys & Borsook, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1924, 62, 1.
5. Kodangekar, Mandlekar & Mehta, *this Journal.*, 1946, 9, 34.
6. Satow, *Tech. Rep. Tohoku Imp. Univ.*, 1921, 2, 2.
7. Van Slyke, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1911, 10, 15.
8. Van Slyke, *ibid.*, 1951, 22, 289.
9. Denis, *ibid.*, 1909, 8, 401.
10. Damodaran, *Biochem. J.*, 1931, 25, 2123.
11. Sørensen *et al.*, *Biochem. Z.*, 1908, 7, 45; *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1910, 64, 120.